

USE OF WINDOWS PRESENTATION FOUNDATION AND WINDOWS FORMS IN WINDOWS APPLICATION PROGRAMMING

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Abstract:

This paper concentrates upon two of the development tools used to develop windows applications and both of them are provided by Microsoft. One quite old and very widely used is Win-Forms which is there since the days of visual basic 6. But now Microsoft came up with a new tool that is called Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF). As compared to Win-Forms, WPF is quite new and introduced with .Net 3.0 as a part of .Net framework. Microsoft has never given a clear statement that WPF is here to replace the Win-Forms or both tools will be there to be used side by side. Both the tools have some pros and cons over each other. So, here in this paper we will present a comparative study of both the tools. Which will help a developer to decide which of the tool is better to develop the application in question. But as Microsoft hasn't cleared that WPF will replace Win-Forms or not, in this paper we assume that both the tools are to be used together.

Key Words: WPF, Win-Forms, Memory, Templates, Controls, Animation, Triggers, Design Options, Layout, Control Design, Procedural Approach, User Interface, Data Binding, Framework & Skinning Structure

1. Introduction:

Although WPF is not a very recent tool and its around here for few years but as compared to Win-Forms it's still a very recent tool. Even today there are lots of developers out there who don't know much about WPF. Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF) is a GUI framework and it is used to create windows applications same as Win-Forms. Both the technologies are launched by Microsoft. WPF is a part of Microsoft .Net framework 3 or higher. As we have already said both of the tools are used for almost same function which is to develop windows application but still WPF has lots of differences as compared to the Win-Forms [1]. The biggest difference between them is that Win-Forms are simply a layer on top of standard windows control; it completely relies on windows environment whereas WPF can be created from the scratch so there are not many dependencies on windows environment. Both the tools have some pros and cons over each other and here we will see those differences, pros and cons in detail. So, readers of this paper can make their decision with ease and without any doubt that which one is better for their application and should be used by them.

2. Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF):

Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF) is a Graphical User Interface (GUI) framework. This is used to create client side applications for windows as well as web based applications. Although in this paper we will only concentrate on windows client side development. WPF is a part of .Net framework 3 and above. Figure 1, depicts the .Net 3.0 Stack with all its main parts.

Figure 1

WPF is capable of designing UI not only with user control and some on screen document support but it supports much more than this. Comparative supported formats for WPF and Win-Forms are listed in table 1.

Table 1: Supported techs in WPF and win-Forms

Technology	Win-Forms	WPF
Graphical Interface like form, user controls etc	Yes	Yes
On Screen Document support	Yes	Yes
Fixed Format Documents	No	Yes
Images	No	Yes
2-D and 3-D Graphics	No	Yes
Video & Audio	No	Yes

Some of you may have seen the things stated above as supported techs by Win-Forms in lots of applications developed using Win-Forms but the support is very limited in use and for that to Win-Forms need to import a handler to some application which actually supports the feature. Like for videos Win-Forms uses Windows Media Player to play videos in your application. For Fixed Format Documents like .PDFs it has to use Adobe's PDF applications or for 3-D graphics Direct 3D can be used etc. Whereas in WPF all these technologies can be incorporated directly in your application. So, there is quite less dependency in other applications and windows environment, if you are using WPF as your development platform. WPF is not only good at styling but it also provides very simple and highly advanced data binding. Over all it is a quite strong tool to develop windows client side apps [2]. Some of the advantages and disadvantages of WPF are as follows:

Advantages of WPF:

- ✓ Very powerful in styling
- ✓ Provides skinned structure for form design.
- ✓ Environment dependency is less so it's easy to create own look and feel.
- ✓ Ability to reuse existing code.
- ✓ Data binding is simple yet highly advanced.
- ✓ Much quicker to develop normal apps. Forms are probably simple, once you are experienced.
- ✓ Futuristic technology for developing advance applications.
- ✓ Supports declarative as well as procedural approach.
- ✓ Procedural methods can be used as and when required.
- ✓ Framework is much smarter and requires quite less code behind to do general things.
- ✓ Apps are much more maintainable due to good data binding and effective declarative code.
- ✓ Excellent layout is provided.
- ✓ Document support is very good and efficient.
- ✓ Multimedia, Audio and video support is very good.
- ✓ Two dimension and three dimension graphics is supported.
- ✓ Also provides support for Win-Forms control.

Disadvantages of WPF:

- ✓ Requires .Net 3.0 or higher.
- ✓ Compared to Win-Forms still some of the controls and definitions are missing.
- ✓ Available support is less as compared to Win-Forms.
- ✓ Requires DX9 compatible graphics card to support advanced graphics.
- ✓ Technology is quite new so learning curve is quite high.

3. Windows Forms (Win-Forms):

Windows form is a platform which is used to develop windows client applications. This platform comes up with a set of managed libraries to provide a clear, object oriented extensible set of classes to support the development of windows applications [3]. It's a graphical Application Programming Interface (API) to facilitate data display and to manage user's interaction with application. Windows Forms has extensive client library to provide interface for accessing graphical UI and graphics of windows operating system using managed coding. Every control in Win-forms is an instance of a class [4]. Its layout and behavior is managed using methods. It provides an event driven architecture, so application developed using windows forms not only takes user inputs but it also waits for specific values entered by user or specific events to occur for their execution. Win-forms has variety of controls available as well as provides option to design the new ones [5]. There are classes to create fonts, brushes, icons and other graphic objects. Visual Studio comes up with a tool called Windows Forms Designer with facility to insert controls in a form, arrange them as per desired layout, provides option to use event handlers and to add code to implement user interaction as desired [6]. Application setting also can be used in Win-forms to create, store and maintain run time state information in XML form. That type of information can be used to get application settings as per user requirement and these setting can be reused for future applications also [7]. Some of the advantages and disadvantages of Windows Forms are as follows:

Advantages of Windows Forms:

- ✓ If needed, extensive documentation is available on the Internet.
- ✓ Tested code and working examples are available in abundance everything is tested thoroughly for years.

- ✓ Some support for WPF is also available
- ✓ lots of 3rd party controls are available in the market to make your job easier
- ✓ Visual Studio designer is somewhat easier for Winforms as compared to WPF, where lots of work has to be done by the programmer to get exactly what is desired.

Disadvantages of Windows Forms:

- ✓ It needs a lot of work to get desired look and feel. So, be prepared to take lots of pain to get it.
- ✓ If third party controls are needed definitely it means some extra cost will be added to your budget

4. Comparative Study:

As we have seen in introduction of WPF and Windows Forms, both technologies are used in developing client end windows applications and both are having some pros and cons. So, one cannot put a clear line that which one is better for the development of windows applications. Rather than having straight choice one has to look for application's needs and has to decide as per requirement. To support his/her decision more clearly now we will come up with tabular comparison of both tools to make comparison and to see that which one of the tool can supports the features needed by an application.

Table 2: Comparative analysis of WPF and win-Forms

Technology	Win- Forms	WPF
Multimedia Support	No	Yes
Skinned Form Design	No	Yes
Form Styling	Weak	Powerful
Graphical Interface like from, user controls etc	Yes	Yes
Designing Own Look	Hard	Easy
Reusability of code	Less	High
Data Binding	Simple	Advanced
Code behind work	High	Less
Learning Curve	Small	High
Procedural Programming Support	Yes	Yes
Documentation availability	Extensive	Medium
Availability of 3rd party tools	High	Low
On Screen Document support	Yes	Yes
Use of Declarative Programming	Less	High
FixedFormat Documents	No	Yes
Images	No	Yes
Futuristic Technology	No	Yes
XAML support	No	Yes
Effort in Binding Data	High	Less
2-D and 3-D Graphics	No	Yes
.Net 3.0 or Higher	Not Required	Required
DX9 Compatible Graphic Card	Not Required	Required
Windows Environment Dependency	More	Less
Tools and Controls available	More	Less
Technology	Old	New
Memory Consumption	Less	High
CPU Load	Less	High
Load Time	High	Less
Availability of Help Forums & Blogs	More	Less
Routed Events	No	Yes
Video & Audio	No	Yes

Table 2 gives tabular comparison for WPF and Win-Forms which can make it easier to choose one of them when a person needs to develop an application. One thing is clear though that it's not good to move to one tool completely for all of your solutions. But wiser decision is that looks in to your application's needs and then decide which one of the tool you want to use. Like if your application needs high multimedia support definitely your first choice will be WPF or if your application needs very advanced data bindings or if your main concern is speed instead of memory usage then you can go for WPF without a doubt. But if you are in reverse situation and for your application saving memory is far more important than speed then you have to go for Windows Forms.

5. Comparison for Memory Uses:

This memory comparison has been done with a small practical scenario created with both tools and then compare the results of memory utilisation, retrieved by diagnostic tools available with Visual Studio 2015. The scenario includes a small application in which 1000 textboxes are created and then rendered on screen.

Reason for using Textbox is that they are quite simple controls and directly available in control classes: in Windows-Forms class is System.Windows.Forms.Control whereas in WPF class is System.Windows.Controls.Primitives.Control. So, any other class is not involved which will reduce the additional overheads. For Windows-Forms when first snapshot is taken application has created 1247 objects which took 94.35KB memory but at the time of second snapshot when all 1000 textboxes are created application has created 14,327 objects which all took 654.77 KB memory.

Objects (Diff)	Heap Size (Diff)
1,247	94.35 KB
14,327 (+13,080 ↑)	654.77 KB (+560.43 KB ↑)

Whereas for WPF at the time of initial snapshot application has created 12,702 objects and consumed 595.80 KB memory whereas when all 1000 textboxes are created application has created 40,432 objects which all consumed 17,689 KB of memory.

Objects (Diff)	Heap Size (Diff)
12,702	595.80 KB
40,432 (+27,730 ↑)	17,689.31 KB (+17,093.51 KB ↑)

It clearly shows that for creating and rendering 1000 textboxes Win-Forms created considerably less objects and took very less memory whereas for same job WPF created too many objects and consumed quite high amount of memory. But there are some other things to observe to get the exact performance factor.

Table 3: Memory Consumption and Load Time Comparison of WPF and Win-Forms

	Initialize		Loaded 1000 Textboxes			Total Load Time
	Size (KB)	Objects Created	Size (KB)	Objects Created	Average Textbox Size bytes	
Windows	94.35	1247	654.77	14327	168	7.636
WPF	595.8	12702	17689.31	404324	727	4.238

Table 3 makes it very clear that in comparison with Win-Forms, WPF's memory consumption is really high that is due to the fact that in WPF, controls are designed in such a way that they need more smaller units to be initialized to create the control but it also shows an interesting fact that even with such a high memory consumption, Load Time for WPF is very less. It means that even if WPF is taking high amount of memory, speed wise WPF is way better than.

6. Conclusion:

After comparing different aspects and pros & cons of both tools we easily can see one thing that deciding one tool for all the applications is not wise. Instead of using one tool always, a person should always first look into its application's need and should look for the elements taken into account in Table 2. If elements he is looking for is mostly supported by Win-Forms then Win-Forms is a good choice coz it is easy to search material and get help for Win-Forms, if needed but if your application has some of the stuff which is not supported by Win-Forms and only supported by WPF then one should opt for WPF. Memory usage and speed also can affect the decision. If your main concern is memory then definitely Win-Forms is your first choice but if memory usage is not the primary factor then WPF will give you better speed. So, which tool is better is mainly depends upon application's requirements.

7. References:

- Andrew, P., Conard, J., & Woodgate, S. (2005). Presenting Windows Workflow Foundation. Sams.
- Reff, M., & O'Neal, J. (2015, October). Using C# and WPF to Create a Dynamic 3D Telemetry Theater and Trajectory Visualization Tool. In International Telemetering Conference Proceedings. International Foundation for Telemetering.
- Burns, S., & Endress, W. (2014, October). Using C# and WPF to Create Fast Plots for Telemetry Analysis on Large Data Sets. In International Telemetering Conference Proceedings. International Foundation for Telemetering.
- Shan, D., Dong, J., Huang, Z., & Xu, J. (2015). Application of Contemporary Programming Techniques in Health Monitoring Software for Suspension Bridges. Ned University Journal of Research, 12(2), 1.
- Lee, A. H. Y., Mccauley, G. R. A. N. T. L. E. Y., Papachristos, J. V., & Heida, F. (2014). U.S. Patent Application No. 14/479,451.
- James, B., & Lalonde, L. (2015). The WPF User Interface. In Pro XAML with C# (pp. 125-158). Apress.
- Li, J., Liu, Q., & Su, H. (2013). Virtual reality method of portal slewing crane based on WPF. Advances in Mechanical Engineering, 5, 320757.